

Education Quarterly Reviews

Srisopha, K. (2022). A Causal Relationship Model of English Language Learning Strategies and Achievement Motivation among Physical Education Students at Thailand National Sports University. *Education Quarterly Reviews*, 5(2), 262-269.

ISSN 2621-5799

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1993.05.02.487

The online version of this article can be found at:

<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

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A Causal Relationship Model of English Language Learning Strategies and Achievement Motivation among Physical Education Students at Thailand National Sports University

Kwanklao Srisopha¹

¹ Thailand National Sports University Chon Buri Campus. Email: ajkwan.s@gmail.com

Abstract

The objectives of this research were 1) to study the level of English language learning strategies, 2) to study the level of English language learning achievement motivation, and 3) to establish and validate a causal relationship model of English language learning strategies and achievement motivation with empirical data. The population of this study was 1,597 second-year physical education students from 17 campuses of Thailand National Sports University. The sample size was determined for 20 people per 1 observed variable (Hair, et al., 2010), in which there were 22 observed variables in this research. The sample size was calculated to be 440 people (20 x 22) and the sample proportion was determined according to the population of each campus. The questionnaire used in the research was a 5-rating scale questionnaire with a content validity ranged between 0.67-1.00 and the reliability value of the English learning strategy questionnaire, the reliability value of the English language learning achievement motivation questionnaire and the reliability value of the whole questionnaire were 0.936, 0.958 and 0.967, respectively. The results of this research indicated that 1) The English language learning strategies of physical education students at Thailand National Sports University were at a moderate level in both overall and individual strategies. 2) The level of English language learning achievement motivation of physical education students at Thailand National Sports University was at a high level and (3) the causal relationship model of English language learning strategies and achievement motivation among physical education students at Thailand National Sports University was consistent with empirical data.

Keywords: English language learning strategies, achievement motivation

1. Introduction

Thailand National Sports University's Physical Education undergraduate students are highly skilled students. They can be a large number of national team athletes who have the opportunity to compete and train abroad on a regular basis, as well as work with foreign coaches. As a result, being able to communicate effectively in English is critical. Students at Thailand National Sports University's Physical Education Department will be motivated to improve their English language skills until they are able to communicate fluently in English, which will be a factor in helping them develop more effective sports skills. However, learning English is difficult for Thai children from elementary to tertiary levels, so teachers need to find a way of teaching and learning to make sure that students are interested in learning, focus on learning to develop students' learning achievements. According to related research

studies, there are several factors influencing the ability to learn English, and one of them is achievement motivation (Chaiwat Bowonwattanasate, 2020 and Sangducan Boonyam, 2018).

Achievement motivation is the drive that propels people to achieve their goals, overcome adversity, and triumph over others. Achievement or competitive motivation affects thoughts, feelings, and behaviors, so achievement motivation is the force that motivates a person to be motivated, to try, to persist. People with high achievement motivation have perseverance, hardworking, planning, setting high expectations and trying to overcome obstacles in order to get the job done well (Preeyaporn Wonganuttaroch, 2005). In regards to learning a second language, Al-Tamimi and Shuib (2009) stated that motivation is a complex variable but can be used to improve learners' learning in order to achieve better foreign language learning outcomes because proper motivation can create behaviors that lead to goals, consistent with Chang and Liu's (2013) notion that language proficiency learners were associated with motivation, causing language learning behaviors to be positively correlated to enhance second language learning.

Language learning strategies are specific methods or techniques that learners use to help learners get the most out of language learning. The use of good learning strategies also results in good language proficiency in learners. (Oxford, 1990). Therefore, to be successful in learning a foreign language, learners must have appropriate and consistent strategies in their study and use those strategies in their studies appropriately and continuously. As Bialystok (1981) said, language-learning strategies are the best way that learners make the most of their language learning to improve their ability to learn that language.

As an English language teacher in a higher education institution, the researcher is interested in studying English language learning strategies and how they influence students' English language learning achievement motivation in order to motivate the research findings in learning English that will lead to the development of students' learning outcomes until they can use for quality communication.

2. Objectives

1. To study the English language learning strategies of Physical Education students at Thailand National Sports University.
2. To study the level of English language learning achievement motivation of Physical Education students at Thailand National Sports University.
3. To establish and validate a causal relationship model of English language learning strategies and achievement motivation among physical education students at Thailand National Sports University with empirical data.

3. Research hypothesis

The causal relationship model of English language learning strategies and achievement motivation among physical education students at Thailand National Sports University is consistent with the empirical data.

4. Research conceptual framework

The purpose of this research was to study the motivation for learning English as it is important for learning English as a second language. Motivation consists of four components: Goal, Effortful behavior, A desire to attend the goal and Attitude. Motivation can be divided into 2 types including integrated motivation and instrumental motivation. It is positively correlated with foreign language learning achievement. (Gardner, 1985). Therefore, developing motivation to learn a second language for students is one of the ways that learners can achieve higher levels of language learning achievement.

Factors affecting motivation to pursue academic achievement that are important are learners (Sophana Sudsomboon, 2021), such as self-worth, attitudes towards learning, relationship between students and friends, relationships between students and parents (Nootchanate Kansamut and Prasopchai Phasunon, 2015) and in

language learning, one of the most important factors that the learner must develop or be developed for learning is a second language learning strategies, according to the Oxford (1990) model of language learning which states that in order to be successful in foreign language learning, students must have strategies to study and use them in their studies appropriately and consistently. It's a self-directed learning. Language learning strategies can be divided into two groups: 1) Direct strategies, consisting of 3 types: memory strategies, cognitive strategies, and compensation strategies, and 2) Indirect strategies consisting of 3 types: metacognitive strategies, affective strategies, and social strategies. In this research, the researchers applied the Oxford English Learning Strategies (1990) and Gardner's Second Language Achievement Motivation (Gardner, 1985) to form a research conceptual framework and "a causal relationship model of English language learning strategies and achievement motivation among physical education students at Thailand National Sports University" as shown in Figure 1 and Figure 2, respectively, as follows:

Figure 1: Research conceptual framework

Figure 2: Theoretical causal relationship model

Research variables

Forecasting variable: English learning strategies, consisting of

- 1) Memory strategies (X_1)
- 2) Cognitive strategies (X_2)
- 3) Compensation strategies (X_3)
- 4) Metacognitive strategies (X_4)
- 5) Affective strategies (X_5)
- 6) Social strategies (X_6)

Criterion variable

English learning achievement motivation (Y)

Method

Population and sample

The population used in the study was 1,597 second-year students in Physical Education from 17 campuses of Thailand National Sports University. The sample size was determined for 20 people per 1 observed variable (Hair, et al., 2010), in which there were 22 observed variables in this research. The sample size was calculated to be 440 people (20 x 22) and the sample proportion was determined according to the population of each campus.

5. Research tool

The tool used in the research was a 5-rating scale questionnaire based on Likert's concept (1967), consisting of a questionnaire on 6 strategies for learning English language strategies as follows: Memory strategies, Cognitive strategies, Compensation strategies, Metacognitive strategies, Affective strategies, and Social strategies with a content validity of 0.67-1.00, the reliability value of the English learning strategy questionnaire of 0.936, the reliability value of the English language learning achievement motivation questionnaire of 0.958 and the reliability value of the whole questionnaire was 0.967.

6. Data analysis results

The results of data analysis of English learning strategies and achievement motivation of 2nd year physical education students of Thailand National Sports University as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation scores for English language learning strategies and achievement motivation among physical education students at Thailand National Sports University

Strategies and motivation	X	SD	Level
1. Memory strategies (X1)	3.43	0.39	Moderate
2. Cognitive strategies (X2)	3.31	0.22	Moderate
3. Compensation strategies (X3)	3.33	0.27	Moderate
4. Metacognitive strategies (X4)	3.39	0.44	Moderate
5. Affective strategies (X5)	3.49	0.42	Moderate
6. Social strategies (X6)	3.30	0.30	Moderate
Total	3.38	0.38	Moderate
English language learning motivation (Y)	3.67	0.46	High

The results of a causal relationship model analysis of English language learning strategies and achievement motivation among physical education students at Thailand National Sports University as shown in Table 2

Table 2: The statistics for the causal relationship of English language learning strategies and achievement motivation among physical education students at Thailand National Sports University

Statistics tested	Statistics	Criteria*
Chi - Square Statistic	3516.691	
Chi - Square Statistic/df	1.801	<3**
degree of freedom : df	1953	
p	.000	>.05**
Goodness of Fit Index : GFI	0.80	0.80***
RMSEA	0.044	<0.08
Comparative Fit Index (CFI)	0.935	>0.90

*Yuth Kaiyawan (2013), ** Bollen (1989), ***MacCallum, R. C., & Hong, S. (1997).

A theoretical causal model of English language learning strategies and achievement motivation among physical education students at Thailand National Sports University as shown in Figure 3 .

Figure 3: A theoretical causal model

7. Conclusion

The results of the research according to the objectives can be summarized as follows:

1. The overall strategies for English language learning for physical education students at Thailand National Sports University was at a moderate level, and when considering each strategy, it was at a moderate level in all strategies.
2. The level of motivation for English language learning achievement of physical education students at Thailand National Sports University was at a high level.
3. A causal relationship model of English language learning strategies and achievement motivation among physical education students of the Thailand National Sports University corresponded to the empirical data. which was in accordance with the research hypothesis taking into account the chi-square (χ^2) which was equal to 3516.691, the probability (p) was .000, degrees of freedom (df) was 1953, the goodness of fit index (GFI) and the root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA) were 0.801 and 0.044, respectively. The reason why probability part (p) was equal to .000 was because the value χ^2 depended on the sample size. The larger of sample size, the higher of χ^2 value. Therefore, the Bollen's (1989) method was used for the revision based on the Chi - Square Statistic/df of 1.801, which was less than 3.

8. Discussion

1. The overall strategies for English language learning for physical education students at Thailand National Sports University were at a moderate level, and when considering each strategy, it was at a moderate level in all strategies. This may be because physical education students are exceptionally talented in sports skills but have a moderate level of academic background in common subjects, especially English. This is consistent with the data from the Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, Chandrakasem Rajabhat University in the year 2/2012. It was found that 75 physical education students enrolled in the English for Communication course. Most of the students had a low level of academic achievement, namely 15 persons got F grade, 28 persons got D grade, 21 persons got D+ grade and 11 persons got C grade. This is considered a high level of concern and should be addressed urgently (Thanomjit Sarot et al., 2016), and in line with the research results of Siwanon Ninpanit (2017) who found that first year students of Valaya Alongkorn Rajabhat University under royal patronage Those enrolled in the VGE 103 English for Communication course in the first semester of Academic Year 2016 used all English language learning strategies at a moderate level.
2. The level of English language learning achievement motivation of physical education students at Thailand National Sports University was at a high level. This may be because when students enter higher education, they realize that learning English is essential to their future work and study, and that English

is also a communication tool that helps in developing athletic proficiency and because after graduating as a graduate, they must be able to use English to work. Wiley and Wrigley (1987) stated that English is important to students and individuals moving to work. This is consistent with the research results of Sudkanung Naruponjirakul and Sirisopha Saenbunwet (2019), which found that the overall level of motivation in learning English among elementary school students, Faculty of Education, Kamphaeng Phet Rajabhat University was at a high level.

3. A causal relationship model of English language learning strategies and achievement motivation among physical education students of the Thailand National Sports University corresponded to the empirical data, which was in accordance with the research hypothesis. This may be because the researcher had formulated a causal relationship model derived from Oxford (1990's) conceptual second language learning strategies which prescribed strategies for learning a second language into 2 groups of strategies: 1) Direct strategies, consisting of 3 types: memory strategies, cognitive strategies, and compensation strategies, and 2) Indirect strategies consisting of 3 types: metacognitive strategies, affective strategies, and social strategies. The strategies of both groups work to support each other.

Strategies that directly affect the motivation for English language learning achievement of physical education students at Thailand National Sports University consist of Cognitive strategies, memory strategies, and compensation strategies with weights of 0.29, 0.32 and 0.69, respectively. This may be because Memory Strategies are techniques that learners use to store important information and to reuse them, which makes learning a language easier for students. Cognitive strategies are techniques that allow learners to connect new and old information or information they already have through critical thinking; this type of strategy can help learners manage language learning more systematically. As for compensation strategies, they are strategies that consist of making theoretical guesses, using synonyms while listening or reading, and using body language and mother tongue to help in speaking and writing skills (Kusom Yamiroudeng, 2018).

Strategies that indirectly affect the English language learning achievement motivation of physical education students at Thailand National Sports University consist of: metacognitive strategies which affect through the cognitive strategies, the affective strategies which affect through the memory strategies, and social strategies which affect through the compensation strategies with weights of 0.96, 0.76 and 0.84, respectively. This is consistent with the research results of Khamkhien (2013) as follows:

Metacognitive Strategies that affect through the Cognitive Strategies may be because Metacognitive Strategies are techniques of attention, commitment, organization, learning planning and self-assessment of the learner's learning, which help learners to manage the association of new and old or existing information and in learning the language in a better system.

Affective strategies that affect through the Memory strategies may be because Affective Strategies are techniques that make learners love the language they are learning. As a result, they have emotional, attitude, and motivation to learn languages and value in language learning which will allow students to be diligent and patient in remembering what they have learned on a regular basis.

Social strategies that affect through the compensation strategies are techniques that encourage learners to learn about communicating with others in a society to aid language learning and improve language skills so they give learners the need for compensation strategies to overcome speaking and writing problems in English.

9. Suggestions for implications

1. English teachers should prepare students by educating and raising awareness of the importance of implementing English language learning strategies.
2. English teachers should organize teaching activities that allow students to apply a variety of English learning strategies.

10. Suggestions for future research

1. Research should be conducted to develop innovative English teaching activities that are appropriate to the nature of physical education students in order to stimulate their motivation to learn English.
2. Research should be conducted to explore other factors affecting the effectiveness of English language learning among physical education students.
3. There should be experimental research by applying language learning strategies to develop English language learning management activities to improve English language learning achievement of physical education students.

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